

Complexes of Lower Valent Rhenium

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Ligands like 2,2'-dipyridyl and 1,10-phenanthroline form complexes with a variety of low-valency ions¹. Some cationic, anionic, and non-electrolytic cyano-complexes of bivalent rhenium containing these ligands have been previously described^{2,3}. Under suitable conditions, these ligands form somewhat stable cationic complexes with trivalent rhenium.

Procedure.—Potassium rhenichloride was intimately mixed with five equivalents of *o*-phenanthroline and the dry mixture was heated in a sealed tube at 245° for 20 minutes. Removal of excess *o*-phenanthroline with benzene, followed by extraction with dry methanol, provided a deep blue-violet solution. The residue remaining after extraction with methanol is under investigation. By careful addition of ether to the methanolic extract, a blue powder separated which was purified by repeatedly dissolving in dry methanol, followed by fractional precipitation with ether. It was dried in vacuum and analysed. {Found: Re, 21.80; N, 10.06; C, 52.12; Cl, 12.60. Calc. for $[\text{Re}^{\text{III}}(\textit{o}\text{-phen})_3]\cdot\text{Cl}_3$: Re, 22.38; N, 10.09; C, 51.88; Cl, 12.78%}.

Trivalency of rhenium in this compound was determined by oxidation with dichromate. The compound was found to be diamagnetic. It is highly soluble in polar solvents like water and alcohols but insoluble in ether, benzene, chloroform, etc. The compound is not very stable in aqueous solution, being easily decomposed with expulsion of phenanthroline. The compound is easily oxidised by common oxidants. It gives less soluble iodide, perchlorate, and tartrate.

An aqueous solution of the compound absorbed strongly in the visible region of the spectrum which was found to be maximum at 550 m μ . The position of the maximum was displaced with change of the solvent medium.

Polarographic reduction of the compound was reversible and corresponded to one-electron change, suggesting reduction of $\text{Re}(\text{III})$ to $\text{Re}(\text{II})$. The half-wave potential was found to be -0.805 V vs. S.C.E. at 23°. Faintly acidic solution of potassium rhenichloride, to which *o*-phenanthroline and ethanol had been added, could be reduced with sodium hypophosphite in absence of air to exhibit a red coloration, which instantaneously reacted with oxygen of air to furnish blue-violet $[\text{Re}(\textit{o}\text{-phen})_3]\text{Cl}_3$ along with the insoluble compound under investigation. The red colour may be due to the bivalent rhenium complex, $[\text{Re}(\textit{o}\text{-phen})_2]\text{Cl}_2$, the isolation of which is being attempted.

1. Herzog and Tanbe, *Angew. Chem.*, 1958, 70, 469.

2. Sen *et al.*, *Science & Culture*, 1962, 28, 290, 387.

3. *Idem*, *ibid.*, 1963, 29, 201.

By increasing the reaction time to 30 hours, a compound of bivalent rhenium was isolated, the properties of which were very similar to those of bis-*o*-phenanthroline-dicyano-rhenium (II)³. {Found: Re, 29.63; C, 46.38; N, 9.02; Cl, 11.31. [Re (*o*-phen)₂Cl₂] requires Re, 30.18; C, 46.66; N, 9.07; Cl, 11.50%}. Details of these investigations will be published later.

Thanks are due to the C.S.I.R., New Delhi, for financial assistance and to the University of Calcutta for providing laboratory facilities.

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Received May 31, 1963.